

Some 3D reconstructions of Scanning Electron Microscope images

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As told by Shanklin, [2016](#), 2D SEM images can be turned into 3D object models. “3D surface modeling that can be created using scanning electron microscope absolutely lead to significant understanding of attributes of microscopic surfaces, such as fracture toughness, crack growth and propagation or fracture resistance” (Shanklin, 2016). More recently, Dong et al., 2024, stressed that “SEM can carry out micro-nano scale three-dimensional measurement,” and that “three-dimensional models can provide more accurate information than two dimensional images”. Besides discussing the “commonly used SEM 3D reconstruction methods”, Dong and coworkers are proposing a new method. The references in Shanklin, 2016, and Dong et al., 2024, are providing the literature on the subject.

Here we show some cases of 3D reconstructions, as done in 2017, with an approach based on a single image. We considered SEM images, usually in grey-scale, turning them into .ppm (ASCII) format. The .ppm file has been read by a Fortran program to create the 3D mesh by means of vertices and faces, saved in .obj file format (see Appendix). The position of the vertex is given by the position x and y of the pixel in .ppm image. The value of the pixel grey tone is giving the z-coordinate of the vertex. Once the .obj file is written, its visualizations can be obtained, for instance, by means of <https://3dviewer.net/> and GIMP software.

Here in the following, we show some cases. **Honeycomb**, as in Sparavigna, 2016, with an Image Courtesy, 2011, Audrius Meskauskas, available [Wikiquote](#); **Pores of freeze-dried solutions** as in Arsiccio et al., 2019; **Chitosan SRT** as from Mohd Yussof et al., 2011; **Microcellular plastic**, as in Sparavigna, 2017, with a Microcellular Plastic Micrograph, developed at Indian Institute of Technology, Delhi. Courtesy: Gandhi.iitdelhi, Wikipedia; **Biochar**, as in Sparavigna et al., 2017, August; **Biochar MDPI** is a 3D mesh obtained from a detail in Fig.5 of Suarez-Riera et al., 2023; **Wood** as in Sparavigna, 2017, Image Courtesy Louisa Howard, at <http://www.cellimagelibrary.org/images/39340>; **Edge Wood** is a detail of an image showing the structure of hardwoods (Oak), Courtesy Mckdandy (the author) at English Wikipedia, https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Hard_Soft_Wood.jpg; **Hexagon** is a detail of Corbaea scandens, Pollen, Rasterelektronenmikroskop, 2007, Courtesy by Marie Majaura, https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Cobaea_scandens1-3.jpg; **Saccaromicete**, from Saccharomyces cerevisiae, SEM image, 2016, <https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/49652>, by M. Das Murtey and P. Ramasamy, [Wikimedia](#); **Pollen Grains** is a detail of an image Courtesy Dartmouth College Electron Microscope Facility, [Wikipedia](#); **Diatom**, a detail from SEM images of pores in diatom frustules, [Nature](#), 2018, by L.E. Aguirre, L. Ouyang, A. Elfving, M. Hedblom, A. Wulff and O. Inganäs, available commons.wikimedia.org; **Worm**, from Scanning electron micrograph of a pair of Schistosoma mansoni, see details at Wikipedia [page](#); **Bassorilievo** and **Turin Shroud**, to show a 3D mesh from a bas-relief and a picture.

HONEYCOMB

Fig.1

Fig.2

PORES OF FREEZE_DRIED SOLUTIONS (LYO files)

Fig.3

Fig.4

Fig.5

Fig.6

Fig.7

CHITOSAN SRT

Fig.8

MICROCELLULAR

Fig.9

BIOCHAR

Fig.10

Fig.11

BIOCHAR MDPI

Fig.12

WOOD

Fig.13

EDGE WOOD

Fig.14

HEXAGON

Fig.15

SACCAROMICETE

Fig.16

POLLEN GRAINS

Fig. 17

Fig.18

DIATOM

Fig.19

WORM

Fig.20

BASSORILIEVO

Fig.21

TURIN SHROUD

Fig.22

Appendix (Fortran Program)

The program reads fort.90 file, that is the .ppm image, and write fort.10, that can be renamed as xxx.obj file.

```
implicit real*8(a-h,o-z)
dimension vett(3000000), ric(530,530,3), ricnew(530,530,3)
read(90,*) n11,n21
read(90,*) ntmax
print *,n11,n21,ntmax
ntot1=n11*n21*3
i=0
      read(90,*)(vett(i),i=1,ntot1)
do i1=1,n11
do i2=1,n21
do i3=1,3
c  print *,i1,i2,i3
      io=io+1
      ric(i2,i1,i3)=vett(io)
end do
end do
end do
print *, '+'
do i1=1,n11
      do i2=1,n21
            do i3=1,3
                  ricnew(i1,i2,i3)=ric(i1,i2,i3)/5.
            end do
      end do
end do
n=n11
nvo=0
io=1
do i=1,n
      do j=1,n
            nvo=nvo+1
      end do
end do
write(10,*)(nvo+5+4*n*2)
do k=0,n-2
      do i=(k*n)+1,(k*n)+1+n-2
            nf=nf+2
      end do
end do
nf=nf+2
ncuf=0
do k=0,3
      do i=nvo+5+(k)*n*2+2,nvo+5+(k)*n*2+2*n-2
            ncuf=ncuf+2
      end do
end do
ncuf=0
nf=nf+ncuf
write(10,*) (nf)

do i=1,n
      do j=1,n
            write(10,*)'v ',i,j,ricnew(j,i,1)
      end do
end do
```

```

write(10,*)v 'io,io,0
write(10,*)v 'io,n,0
write(10,*)v 'n,io,0
write(10,*)v 'n,n,0
write(10,*)v '0,0,0
do i=1,n
write(10,*)v 'i,io,0
write(10,*)v 'i,io,ricnew(io,i,1)
end do
do i=1,n
write(10,*)v 'i,n,0
write(10,*)v 'i,n,ricnew(n,i,1)
end do
do i=1,n
write(10,*)v 'io,i,0
write(10,*)v 'io,i,ricnew(i,io,1)
end do
do i=1,n
write(10,*)v 'n,i,0
write(10,*)v 'n,i,ricnew(i,n,1)
end do
do k=0,n-2
do i=(k*n)+1,(k*n)+1+n-2
write(10,*)f 'i,i+1,(i+n)
write(10,*)f 'i+1,(i+n),(i+1+n)
end do
end do
write(10,*)f 'nvo+1,nvo+2,nvo+3
write(10,*)f 'nvo+2,nvo+3,nvo+4
nvo=nvo
do k=0,3
do i=nvo+5+k*n*2+2,nvo+5+k*n*2+2*n-2
write(10,*)f 'i-1,i,i+1
write(10,*)f 'i,(i+1),(i+2)
end do
end do
end

```

In the part of the program, where ricnew(i1,i2,i3) is defined, the reader can easily change the function, to obtain a different reconstruction.

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